

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART III. STUDIES IN THE MICHAEL
CONDENSATION OF 1-ACETYL-3:4-DIHYDRONAPHTHALENE
AND ACETOACETIC ESTER*

BY PRATUL CHANDRA MUKHARJI

Michael condensation of 1-acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene with ethyl sodio-acetoacetate leads to the formation of ethyl 4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -hexahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylate, showing that during the formation of the third ring, ring-closure involves the keto group of the acetoacetic ester residue.

In Part II of this series (this *issue*, p. 365) it has been pointed out that starting from the tricyclic keto-esters (III) and (IV, R=OMe) it may be possible to prepare the dicarboxylic acids (V) and (VI, R=OMe), where the two carboxyl groups in all likelihood may appear in the *trans* configuration. Following the method employed by Bachmann and Kushner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1963) to prepare *trans*-8-methylhydrindanone from *trans*-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid, it may be possible ultimately to synthesise steroid ketones with the rings C/D fused in the *trans* position, starting from the above dicarboxylic acids. The present work has been carried out with a view to finding out a general method for the synthesis of the required type of tricyclic keto-esters (III) and (IV, R=OMe).

Barrett, Cook and Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1066) have already shown that Michael's reaction of acetyl*cyclohexene* and ethyl sodioacetoacetate leads to the formation of ethyl *trans*-4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -octahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylate (IX). The appearance of this compound demonstrates that ring-closure of the intermediate diketone (VIII) first formed involves the carbonyl group of the acetoacetic ester moiety in preference to the other carbonyl group which is comparatively hindered, possibly due to the proximity of the *cyclohexane* residue. A preliminary study has therefore been made with the readily available 1-acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (II, R=H) in order to see if the reaction with ethyl sodioacetoacetate pursue the above course to yield the tricyclic keto-ester (IV, R=H) of the required type. Besides the simplicity of this method, a further advantage lies in the fact, that the above reaction leads to the *trans* fusion of the two *cycloparaffin* rings (Barrett, Cook and Linstead, *loc. cit.* Ruzicka, Koolhass and Wind, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, **14**, 1151; Hückel, *Annalen*, 1925, **441**, 1) exactly as is necessary for the ultimate end in view. The results of this preliminary study confirm that the ring-closure in this case also involves the keto group of the acetoacetic ester residue, as has been found in the reaction between acetyl*cyclohexane* and acetoacetic ester. It can be reasonably anticipated therefore that in the case of 6-methoxy-1-acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (II, R=OMe) and 9-methyl-1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -octahydronaphthalene (I), the reaction with ethyl sodioacetoacetate will pursue the course observed in the above cases.

* A preliminary note was published in the *Science & Culture*, 1947, **18**, 39.

1-Acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (II, R=H; cf. Birch and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 503) has been prepared from 3:4-dihydronaphthoyl chloride and cadmium dimethyl. The Michael reaction of ethyl sodioacetoacetate with the above ketone proceeds smoothly to yield a highly crystalline phenanthrene derivative which may be represented by either of the structures (IV, R=H) or (VII, R=H). The compound appears to be stereochemically pure and possibly belongs to the *trans* series as can be deduced from its method of formation. On catalytic hydrogenation of the double bond of this phenanthrene derivative, followed by hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid, a solid acid (m. p. 187-89°) is obtained, the formation of which conclusively proves that in this case also the ring-closure as expected involves the carbonyl group of the acetoacetic ester residue to yield the desired compound (IV, R=H). Had the ring-closure pursued the other possible route to produce the isomeric compound (VII, R=H), then the corresponding dihydro-ester, being β -keto ester derivative, would have suffered decarboxylation during hydrolysis to yield a neutral ketone. In keeping with this, it has also been found that the phenanthrene derivative (IV, R=H) as well as its dihydro derivative do not produce any coloration with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution.

Experiments are now well under way for the synthesis of the tricyclic keto-ester (III) and (IV, R=OMe).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1-Acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (II, R=H).—This ketone was prepared from 3:4-dihydro-1-naphthoyl chloride and cadmium dimethyl (cf. Carson and Prout, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 46). To a Grignard reagent, prepared from methyl iodide (36 g.), magnesium (6 g.) and ether (90 c.c.), cooled in ice was added in one portion anhydrous powdered cadmium chloride (10.8 g.). After removal from ice-bath the mixture was stirred for 5 minutes and the ether distilled off on a steam-bath, to get a dark semisolid mass. Dry benzene (50 c.c.) was then added and distillation resumed till benzene ceased to distil. Dry benzene (50 c.c.) was then added and the mixture vigorously stirred to get the solid uniformly dispersed in the medium. The acid chloride (27 g.), prepared from 3:4-dihydro-1-naphthoic acid (Sowinski, *Ber.*, 1891 **24**, 2357) and thionyl chloride according to Birch and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) in benzene (30 c.c.), was then added to the above benzene solution, cooled in ice during the course of about 10 minutes with continuous stirring. After about 15 minutes, the mixture was refluxed for 1 hour and the complex decomposed with iced sulphuric acid. The benzene solution was separated and washed with water, dilute bicarbonate of soda solution and benzene removed under reduced pressure. The residue was then heated on a steam-bath with 10% caustic soda solution for 5-10 minutes. The product was then isolated in the usual manner and distilled. The ketone distilled at 160°-165°/10 mm. as a pale yellow oil, yield 16 g. (Found: C, 83.1; H, 6.8. $C_{12}H_{12}O$ requires C, 83.7; H, 7.0 per cent). The *semicarbazone* after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 206°-208° (Birch and Robinson, *loc. cit.*, m. p. 208°).

Michael's Condensation of 1-Acetyl-3:4-dihydronaphthalene with Ethyl Acetoacetate: Formation of Ethyl 4-Keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -hexahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylate (IV, R=H).—The above unsaturated ketone (15 g.) was added to the sodio salt of ethyl acetoacetate, prepared from acetoacetic ester (21 g.), sodium (2.1 g.) and absolute alcohol (24 c.c.), cooled in ice bath. The mixture was left at the ordinary temperature for 5 days when a reddish brown thick solution was obtained. It was then heated on a steam-bath for 3 hours, cooled and decomposed with iced acetic acid. The ether extract of the heavy oil was washed with water, dilute caustic soda solution, again with water and dried. From the viscous oil obtained after the evaporation of the solvent, ethyl acetoacetate was removed by distillation under diminished pressure, and the residue on treatment with dilute alcohol gave beautiful silky needles, and was recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 102°-103°, yield 6 g. (Found: C, 75.56; H, 7.13. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2$ requires

C, 76.05 ; H, 7.04 per cent). The product did not produce any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Catalytic Hydrogenation of the above compound: Formation of Ethyl 4-Keto-2-methyloctahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylate.—A suspension of the above unsaturated keto-ester (4 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of Adam's catalyst (0.1 g.). Absorption of hydrogen took place very rapidly and with the progress of hydrogenation the crystals gradually passed into solution. After the theoretical amount of hydrogen had been taken up, the clear alcoholic solution was filtered off, alcohol removed under reduced pressure, and the residue distilled. The dihydro-ester boiled at 183° - $185^{\circ}/4$ mm. as a colourless, viscous oil which did not solidify. (Found : C, 75.1 ; H, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 75.52 ; H, 7.7 per cent). It did not produce any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The *oxime* prepared by the alcohol-pyridine method crystallised from methyl alcohol in clusters of silky needles, m. p. 217° .

Hydrolysis of the above Dihydro-ester.—The above dihydro-ester (2 g.) was refluxed on a wire gauze with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 20 hours. The ether extract of the gummy product was washed three times with dilute bicarbonate of soda solution. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was distilled off. No appreciable residue remained behind in the flask after the removal of the ether.

The bicarbonate extract was then carefully acidified, when an oily substance separated which, however, solidified after some time. The solid was dried overnight in a vacuum desiccator and then crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether and subsequently from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 187 - 89° with previous shrinking at 177° . (Found : C, 73.82 ; H, 7.2. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.4 ; H, 7.0 per cent).

The author's grateful thanks are due to Dr. P. C. Mitter and Prof. S. N. Bose for their keen interest and encouragement during the course of this investigation, to Dr. P. C. Dutt, D.Sc. for a gift of the starting materials and to Mr. N. Ghosh M.Sc. for the microanalysis of some of the compounds.